

Higher Education in India – Issues, Challenges and Suggestions

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Abstract

In this review paper we have discussed the ambiguous concepts of higher education that is used in the literatures all over world. The study has tried to trace the higher education in India form the long past. Then we have discussed present status of higher education in India and the recent trend in Indian higher education. The issues like Quantity of Institution, Fields of Education, Enrolment Pattern, Teacher Availability, Constitutional Provision on Higher Education, Disparity in Access to Higher Education, Governance Practice, Quality Control Mechanism, Trend in Finance has been discussed briefly. Recent trends like privatization and globalization emerging in the field of Indian higher education was also highlighted in this analysis.

Keywords: Higher education, Opportunities and challenges, Enrolment.

Introduction

The importance of higher education has been clearly expressed by our first Prime Minister Mr. Jawaharlal Nehru in the following words: “A university stands for humanism, for tolerance, for reason, for the adventure of the ideas and for the search of truth. It stands for onward march of human race towards even higher objectives. If the universities discharge their duties adequately, then it well with the nation and the people”. It indicates that higher education occupies a crucial position in education system of a nation as it affects the overall development of a country.

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyse the present status of higher education system in India.
2. To highlight the opportunities and challenges faced by the higher education system in India.
3. Suggestions for improving quality of higher education and

Data and Methodology

The study is mainly based on secondary data which is collected from Ministry of higher education Government of India, University Grants Commission reports, corporate expert’s opinion and other published and unpublished reports which is relevant to the study. For

analysing primary and secondary data, simple statistical tools like percentages and averages have been used to interpret the data. Apart from this, tables, charts, graphs; pictures have been chosen for responding the data at relevant places.

Higher Education in India

India is one the oldest civilizations on earth. Also known as Bharat and Hindustan and officially termed as the ‘Republic of India’, it is the largest liberal democracy of the world. India is divided into 28 states and 7 union territories. India is also the land of the Vedas - the oldest scriptures in the world. It is divided in four-volumes and is regarded as the storehouse of national thoughts. Today, India is the world’s seventh largest country in terms of area and second in terms of population. The sights, the ancient temples and the lush paddy fields make the country unique and amazing. It has 22 major languages with 844 dialects, making this country and its people culturally diverse. The secular nature of India has attracted philosophers and researchers from across the globe to explore India.

India possesses a highly developed higher education system and it is the third largest in the world next to China and United States. Higher Education in India refers to the education obtained after completing 12 years of schooling or equivalent and is of the duration of at least nine months (full time) or after completing 10 years of schooling and is of the duration of at least 3 years.

Also, India has the advantage of English being the primary language apart from the respective regional languages in higher education and research. In India, unlike in western countries, higher education is predominantly a public sector activity and it is perceived as public good. In response to increasing expectations of the people in the country, the central government continues to play a leading role in the formulation and implementation of educational policies and action plans. At the apex level, the University Grants Commission is the main governing body and it embodies the enforcement of its standards, advises and makes recommendations to the government.

Higher Education Institutions in India

The institutions of higher learning in India fall into the following broad categories:

1. **Universities:** These are established by an Act of Parliament or State Legislature and are of unitary or affiliating type. They are called Central Universities and State Universities respectively.
2. **Deemed to be Universities:** These institutions are given deemed to be university status by the Central Government on the recommendation of the UGC in terms of Section 3 of the UGC Act. Some of these institutions offer advanced level courses in a particular field or specialization while others award general degrees.
3. **Private Universities:** These are established by various State governments through their own legislation.
4. **Institutes of National Importance:** These Institutes are declared as such by the Government of India by an Act of Parliament and are empowered to award degrees. In some cases, such Institutes are also set up by the Government through an Act of State Legislation.
5. **Premier Institutes of Management:** These are the Institutes that have been set up by the Central Government and are outside the formal university system. They offer Post-Graduate Diploma Programmes which are equivalent to Master’s Degree Programmes in area of management.

Challenges

The challenges confronting India are manifold. In its quest for modernization and pursuit of economic growth, aimed at lifting hundreds of millions of people out of poverty, providing high quality education and healthcare to its population are the greatest challenges that India has to address. The policy makers and the political executive in India should address the following challenges in reforming the higher education system.

1. How to create an equitable and accessible higher education system of high quality?
2. How to foster competition in providing education services and offer choice to the students?
3. How to promote the importance of a true liberal education?
4. How to enhance public financial provision for higher education?
5. How to establish an independent regulatory framework to ensure standards and quality?

Opportunities

While the challenges are manifold, there are quite a few opportunities and strengths that India should take advantage of, some of which are outlined below:

1. Young demographic profile, (% of 18-24 age group)
2. Hard working, ambitious, motivated youngsters.
3. Huge demand for quality education.
4. Culture and society that values education and treasures scholarship.
5. Parents willing to spend significant resources (110,000 students studying abroad spend approx \$ 1 billion/year)
6. Graduates no longer seek a cushy government job and are willing to compete in the market.
7. Impressive infrastructure that can be redeployed.
8. Non-monetary inputs that can make a difference

Suggestions for improving quality of higher education

There are some suggestions and Expectations from Government, Industry, Educational Institutions, Parents and Students for improving quality of higher education.

Student-Centred Education and Dynamic Methods

Methods of higher education also have to be appropriate to the needs of learning to learn, learning to do, learning to be and learning to become. Student-centred education and employment of dynamic methods of education will require from teachers new attitudes and new skills. Methods of teaching through lectures will have to subordinate to the methods that will lay stress on self-study, personal consultation between teachers and pupils, and dynamic sessions of seminars and workshops. Methods of distance education will have to be employed on a vast scale.

Examination Reforms

Examination reforms, gradually shifting from the terminal, annual and semester examinations to regular and continuous assessment of student's performance in learning must be implemented.

International Cooperation

Universities in India have been a primary conduit for the advancement and transmission of knowledge through traditional functions such as research, innovation, teaching, human resource development, and continuing education. International cooperation is gaining importance as yet another function. With the increased development of transport and communication, the global village is witnessing a growing emphasis on international cooperation and action to find satisfactory solutions to problems that have global dimensions and higher education is one of them.

To Increase Quantity of Universities

We need more universities because we are more in number and present number of universities is too less. On 13th June, 2005 Government of India constituted a high level advisory body known as National Knowledge Commission (NKC) to advise the PM about the state of education in India and measures needed to reform this sector. It was headed by Sam Pitroda and submitted its report in November 2007. NKC has recommended setting up of 1500 universities by 2015 so that gross enrolment ratio increases to 15 percent. It has also called for establishing an Independent Regulatory Authority for Higher Education (IRAHE) to monitor the quality of overall higher education in India.

Cross Culture Programmes

After education, tour to every the places in India and world as far as possible with the cooperation of government is necessary so that one can understand about people, culture, arts, literature, religions, technological developments and progress of human society in the world.

World Class Education

Indian government is not giving priority to the development of Standard in education. India must aspire for the international standard in education. Many national universities like in the USA, UK, Australia, etc. allow studies in higher education for foreign students in their countries and through correspondence courses as well. In the same way India Universities of world class education can also offer courses of studies to foreign students taking advantage of the globalization process. To achieve that goal it must adopt uniform international syllabus in its educational institutions.

High-tech Libraries

Our university libraries have a very good collection of books, but they are all in mess. A library must be online and conducive for serious study. Indian universities should concentrate more on providing quality education which is comparable to that of international standards.

Personality Development

Finally, education must be for the flowering of personality but not for the suppression of creativity or natural skill. In the globalized world opportunity for the educated people are naturally ample in scope. As a result business process outsourcing (BPO) activities have increased competition in the world trade leading towards the production of quality goods and their easy availability everywhere in the world market. That is the way the world can be developed for peace, prosperity and progress by able and skilful men.

Conclusion

A lot of commissions and committees appointed by the government for suggesting reforms have also pinned upon same obstacles in the Indian Higher Education. But there has been sheer dearth of courage and a political will. It is also important that the way attempts have been made to reform secondary level education in schools, higher education needs to be reformed too. It is high time that universities cater to the growing demand of students or else this human resource boon will soon prove to be population bane for the economy. Though these are clearly positive trends, the Indian higher education system continues to demonstrate many structural shortcomings which in turn create challenges in meeting future expectations. Inequity is also pervasive in the system, with the GERs of women and backward castes being much lower than the national average. However, finally achieving India's 30% gross enrolment ratio objective by 2030 plans requires solutions that combine the needs of policy makers, employers and youth Expectations of/from various stakeholders – Students, Industry, Educational Institutions, Parents, Government.

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